

FABRICATION OF 2-D PAN FIBER-PITCH MATRIX CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES USING PREPREG TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Two-dimensional PAN fiber-pitch matrix carbon-carbon composites have been successfully in-house fabricated at Southern Illinois University at Carbondale using a prepreg technique. This technique involves mixing fiber weaves and fine pitch powder under certain conditions presented in this report. Process parameters, such as stabilization and carbonization conditions, are also examined. Emphasis of this research has been placed on the oxidation stabilization process, which is a key step in the prevention of bloating of matrix pitch during carbonization. An oxidation temperature of 200°C has been found optimal for the pitches used in this study. Both polarized light microscopy and scanning Auger microprobe results have shown that matrix is much more susceptible to oxidation than the fibers.

KEYWORDS : carbon/carbon; fabrication; oxidation-stabilization; prepreg; microstructure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pitches are an attractive material as the matrix precursor of carbon-carbon (C-C) composites, primarily due to their high carbon yield as well as ease to graphitize. Their microstructure can be tailored, such as converting from isotropic to anisotropic carbon under certain conditions¹. The high carbon yield, generally, can be obtained by low heating rate, high pressure carbonization² or cross-linking treatment prior to carbonization³.

In a relatively recent report, White et. al⁴ found that oxidation stabilization prior to carbonization had been an effective procedure in the prevention of bloating of mesophase pitch during carbonization, accompanied by an increase in carbon yield. This stabilization technique ap-

pears promising for eliminating , in some cases, the need for high pressure autoclaves or hot presses to restrain pitches from bloating during carbonization, resulting in a cost reduction in C-C fabrication.

The present study investigates the fabrication of 2-d PAN fiber-pitch matrix C-C composites using a prepreg technique, which can be easily scaled up to produce large pieces. Emphasis of this study is placed on the oxidation stabilization process. Two types of pitch, isotropic and 80% mesophase, are used as the matrix precursor for fabrication of C-C composites.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Raw Materials: Commercial 8-harness satin weave Threl T300-3K continuous fiber, produced by Amoco Inc. , was used as the reinforcement. The fiber has a density of $1.78/\text{cm}^3$, tensile strength of 3800 MPa and modulus of 230 GPa. An isotropic pitch, Aerocarb 70, produced by Ashland Petroleum Company, and a commercial 80% mesophase pitch, produced by the same company, were used as matrix precursors. Some characteristics of such pitches are shown in Table 1.

2.2. Fabrication: Two different methods were used to fabricate the PAN-pitch preforms. A prepreg technique was used for Aerocarb 70, whereas a dry weave-powder sandwich technique was used for the 80% mesophase pitch. The process conditions given below for the two techniques are the optimal ones, according to the results of a series of preliminary studies. In the prepreg technique, the Aerocarb 70 pitch was first ground to a fine powder form. The fine powder (roughly $500\ \mu\text{m}$) was weighed, uniformly distributed on the woven carbon cloths, and heat treated at 400°C for 50 hours in N_2 atmosphere. During this heat treatment, the pitch melted and impregnated into the cloths, forming prepregs. Some volatiles were taken out during this heat treatment. The cut prepregs (six layers in most cases) were then stacked in a stainless steel mold, and hot-press molded at temperatures ranging from 350 to 400°C and pressures from 0.28 to 0.55 MPa.

In the case of 80% mesophase pitch, the preforms were formed by hot-press molding of six layers of dry carbon cloth, each of which was sandwiched by controlled-weight ground pitch powder. The hot press molding was carried out at 425°C and a pressure between 0.28 and 0.55 MPa.

2.3. Oxidation Stabilization: The hot-pressed preforms (approximately 2 mm in thickness) were cut into specimens of 10 mm x 50 mm by a diamond saw, placed in a quartz tube, and oxidized by 100% oxygen. Temperatures of 200, 250, and 300°C and an oxygen flow rate of 80 sccm were used for stabilization. The oxidized specimens were subsequently carbonized in N_2 atmosphere to 1000°C at a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{hr}$.

2.4. Microstructure and SAM Characterization: Microstructure of the composites was char-

acterized using a polarized light microscope. Oxygen distribution of some stabilized specimens was analyzed using a scanning Auger microprobe (SAM).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Fabrication of Preforms: Aerocarb 70 and 80% mesophase pitch matrix preforms were fabricated according to the fabrication methods, as summarized in Fig. 1. Process parameters and general characteristics of the two preforms are shown in Table 2. The two preforms were hot-press molded under the same condition, and in neither was delamination observed. It is noted that, although higher in pitch weight fraction by 6%, the Aerocarb 70 preform had a thickness approximately 17% smaller than the 80% mesophase preform. This indicates that the prepreg technique is a potentially better method for the production of a dense 2-d C-C composite. In the 80% mesophase matrix preform, a large number of pores were present as a result of insufficient penetration of the pitch into individual fiber bundles, as shown in Fig. 2. Comparatively, the Aerocarb 70 preform appears much denser; and, from a scaling-up point of view, the prepreg technique also appears more promising.

3.2. Oxidation Stabilization: The weight change of the Aerocarb 70 preform with time at 200°C was gradual and rather smooth, as shown in Fig. 3. The weight gain was not yet saturated after 65 hours, although at a lower rate. Up to 30 hours, the weight gain kept a linear relationship with the square root of oxidation time, Fig. 4, indicating a diffusion-controlled reaction.

In the case of the 80% mesophase pitch preform, the weight gain- $t^{1/2}$ relationships are generally nonlinear. As shown in Fig. 5, the weight gain was saturated to a level of 2.7% after about 20 hours of oxidation at 200°C. Figure 5 also shows the weight change data for 250°C and 300°C. Following initial rapid weight changes, a slow weight loss rate was observed when oxidized at 250°C. A consistently rapid weight loss was observed when oxidized at 300°C, which was obviously too high for stabilization of the pitch. According to these results, the proper temperatures for oxidation stabilization of the pitch should not exceed 250°C to achieve a high carbon yield. The causes to the different weight change behavior between the two pitches are not clear at this time.

3.3. Carbonization: Effectiveness for restriction of bloating/delamination by oxidation stabilization was tested through a carbonization treatment to 1000°C at a heating rate of 10°C/hr. The results have shown that certain stabilization treatments were effective not only in restricting bloating/delamination, but also in increasing carbon yield for both pitches during carbonization. It is interesting, as shown in Fig. 6, that longer oxidation times (and thus greater weight gain, except those oxidized at 300°C) do not necessarily result in high carbon yields. To achieve the best results, suitable ranges for oxidation temperature and time are required.

For example, a suitable oxidation time and temperature for Aerocarb 70 would be about 20 hours and 200°C, respectively, whereas those for 80% mesophase pitch preforms would be about 5 hours and 200°C. For both pitches, too long an oxidation time reduced their carbon yields in carbonization, although bloating/delamination could be effectively controlled. In addition to those stabilized at 200°C, the carbonization weight changes for the 80% mesophase preforms stabilized at 250°C and 300°C were also measured, as shown in Fig. 7. It is clear that as the oxidation stabilization temperature was too high, the weight loss in carbonization significantly increased. For example, the carbonization weight loss of the specimen stabilized for 65 hours at 300°C showed a weight loss as high as 19%. Since the matrix content was 40 wt%, in this preform, the carbon yield of the matrix pitch was calculated to be 53%, compared to 75% when stabilized at 200°C.

3.4. Microstructural Characterization: The microstructure of stabilized as well as carbonized composites comprising both Aerocarb 70 and 80% mesophase pitch matrices was characterized by polarized light microscopy. Both carbonized composites have shown a relatively thick (> 20 μm , depending on oxidation condition) optically isotropic layer for stabilized specimens, in contrast to a thin (approximately 5 μm) isotropic layer for non-stabilized specimens, as shown in Fig. 8. Such a thin isotropic layer, formed due to the oxidation which occurred during hot press molding, was obviously insufficient to effectively "stabilize" the preforms, and a separate stabilization treatment was needed. Once stabilized, the pitch molecular structure became rigid, due to oxygen-induced cross linking, and able to survive the subsequent carbonization from bloating.

The stabilized thickness, i.e., thickness of the isotropic layer, was measured on three carbonized Aerocarb 70 matrix composite specimens stabilized at 200°C for 20, 30, and 65 hours, respectively. Such measurement was made only on the Aerocarb 70 composites due to their originally isotropic structure which allowed the stabilized layer more easily distinguished from the internal non-stabilized, anisotropic structure. This internal anisotropic structure was formed during carbonization, when the isotropic pitch melted and converted, through mesophase transition, to an anisotropic structure.

It should be noted that, in stabilized and carbonized Aerocarb 70 composites, the oxidized, isotropic layer was not only present as a surface "crust", but also observed in the regions around fiber bundles as well as pores and cracks. This is because oxygen could easily penetrate into preforms through cracks and pores, and oxidize adjacent to them. The depth of stabilization was plotted, using the limited data, against the square root of stabilization time for the Aerocarb 70 composites, as shown in Fig. 9. According to the roughly linear relationship between the depth and square root of oxidation time and the adoption of such a simple rela-

relationship as $x = (Dt)^{1/2}$, the diffusivity of oxygen in the isotropic Aerocarb 70 pitch at 200°C, D , was calculated to be $6.9 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^2/\text{sec}$. A potential problem to such optical microscopic measurement, however, should be mentioned at this point. That is that many microcracks of sizes beyond resolution of the optical microscope could possibly exist in the matrix pitch, which could provide easy paths for oxygen penetration and cause the measured oxidation thicknesses far greater than the true ones.

3.5. Preliminary SAM Results: Oxygen distribution of a stabilized (300°C, 65 hours) 80% mesophase pitch matrix preform was analyzed using a scanning Auger microprobe (SAM). Prior to analysis, the mechanically polished specimen was sputter cleaned to remove surface contaminants. Both regions near oxidized surface and in the interior of the sputter-cleaned sample cross-section were analyzed and oxygen distribution mapped.

The SAM results showed that oxygen had penetrated into the preform matrix as deep as tens of microns, in agreement with the optical microscopic observation described above. Compared to that in the matrix, the oxygen concentration within individual fibers was much lower.

Figure 10 is an example showing oxygen distribution in a longitudinal fiber bundle region near the oxidized surface. The oxygen map, Fig. 10 (b), clearly showed that oxygen contents within fibers were much lower than those in adjacent matrix regions. Figure 11 (a) is a higher-magnification transverse section of a fiber located on the edge of a fiber bundle. Its corresponding oxygen map, Fig. 11 (b), also showed a much lower oxygen content inside a relatively thin oxygen-concentrated layer. This concentration variation near fiber surface was not artificially caused by an edge effect, as indicated by the fact that, for those fibers in the interior of a bundle, such concentration variation was no longer observed, Fig. 12.

Figure 13 is an oxygen line scan superimposed on a polished, longitudinal section of a region near the oxidized surface. It can be seen that wherever the scan line intersected a piece of matrix fragments attached to the fiber surface, the oxygen concentration "jumps" abruptly. The oxygen concentration in the interior of fibers was too low to be detected, as shown in the region between "A" and "B", marked in Fig. 13. This, again, confirms that the matrix was oxidized to a much greater extent than fibers at the same depth beneath an oxidized preform surface. The oxygen concentration at the point "X" was determined, through point analysis, to be approximately 12.5 atomic %.

4. CONCLUSIONS

(1) Two-dimensional carbonized PAN fiber-pitch matrix C-C composites were successfully in-house fabricated using a prepreg technique. Compared to the fiber-powder sandwich technique, the prepreg technique provides a better method for fabrication of dense and uniform

composites.

(2) Suitable oxidation stabilization treatments were found effective not only in restriction of bloating/delamination of the composites during carbonization, but also in increase in carbon yield. The best stabilization condition was determined to be about 20 hours at 200°C for the Aerocarb 70 preforms, and about 5 hours at 200°C for the 80% mesophase preforms.

(3) The stabilized layer was present not only as a surface crust, but also deep in the composite around fiber bundles as well as pores and cracks, due to their easy paths for oxygen penetration. Both polarized light microscopy and SAM showed that matrix was much more susceptible to oxidation than the fibers.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge Dr. Maurice A. Wright of the Materials Technology Center at Southern Illinois University at Carbondale for financial support for this project, and Dr. Margaret Genisio of the Materials Technology Center at Southern Illinois University in Carbondale for helpful discussion on this work.

6. REFERENCES

1. E. Fitzer, *Carbon*, 25, 163 (1987)
2. L. E. McAllister and W. L. Lachman, *Handbook of Composites*, Elsevier, New York, 1983, pp. 109, 175.
3. E. Fitzer, W. Hüttner and L. A. Manocha, *Carbon*, 18, 291 (1980)
4. J. L. White and P. M. Sheaffer, *Carbon*, 27, 607 (1989)

Table 1. Characteristics of pitches used in this study

	Aerocarb 70	80%mesophase
Helium Density (g/cm ³)	1.25	1.30
T _g (°C)	171	250
Softening Point (°C)	208	330

Table 2. Preforms characteristics

	Matrix pitch	
	Aerocarb 70	80%mesophase pitch
Pitch wt%	40.0	37.8
Hot-press Temp. (°C)	360	425
No. of layers	6	6
Preform thickness (mm)	2.23	2.71
Delamination	No	No

Fig. 1. Fabrication flow chart

Fig. 2. Optical micrograph of 80%mesophase pitch matrix preform.

Fig. 3. Weight gain in oxidation syabilization of Aerocarb70 matrix preform at 200°C.

Fig. 4. Weight gain in oxidation stabilization of Aerocarb70 matrix preform at 200°C.

Fig. 5. Weight change in oxidation stabilization of 80%mesophase pitch matrix preform.

Fig.6. Weight change in oxidation stabilization and carbonization

Fig. 7. Weight loss in carbonization for 80%mesophasepitch matrix preforms stabilized at 200, 250, and 300°C.

Fig. 9. Stabilized thickness of Aerocarb 70 matrix composites oxidized at 200°C.

Fig. 8. Polarized light micrographs of Aerocarb 70 composite with (a) and without (b) oxidation stabilization.

Fig. 10. Oxygen distribution in a longitudinal fiber bundle near oxidized (300°C, 65 hours) surface of 80% mesophase preform.

Fig. 11. Oxygen distribution of transverse fiber on edge of a fiber bundle near oxidized (300°C, 65 hours) surface of 80%mesophase preform.

Fig. 12. Oxygen distribution of transverse fiber at center of a fiber bundle near oxidized (300°C, 65 hours) surface of 80%mesophase preform.

Fig. 13. Oxygen line scan superimposed on longitudinal fiber bundle near oxidized (300°C, 65 hours) surface of 80%mesophase preform.

